

Madhya Pradesh Journal of Social Sciences

(A Biannual Journal of M.P. Institute of Social Science Research, Ujjain)

ISSN: 0973-855X (Vol. 28, No. 1, June 2023, pp. 74-89)

UGC-CARE (Group-I)

Objectification and Psychological Well-Being across Gender: A Study on Urban Indian Adults

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Objectification refers to reducing a human to a mere object and placing all focus on the body, without acknowledging the mind or personality. When people start indulging in treating themselves as objects, it is known as self-objectification. In recent years, people, irrespective of their gender, are inundated with fixed standards of body and beauty through the profound prevalence of media. The present study is mixed-method research and was conducted with the objective to explore self-objectification and psychological well-being among urban adults (N=150) using quantitative (Self-Objectification Beliefs and Behaviours Scale and Ryff's PWB Scale) and qualitative (semi-structured interview) measures. Data were analysed using SPSS and significant results were reported. Qualitative analysis (thematic analysis) revealed that interviewees were more focused on their physical appearance, rather than on their feelings. They were fine with making changes to their bodies to look more attractive to others, even at the expense of discomfort.

1. Introduction

The human body makes up the basis of the distinction between the sexes. The determinants of differentiation are not just biological but also

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include social and cultural aspects. In doing so, one type of body or sex (usually, male) is often regarded as superior to others, thus devaluing the other sexes. This positioning of sexes has to do little with the biological aspect, and more with the socialisation and power status of men, women and other sexes in society. While doing so, people often end up objectifying the other sex.

1.1 *Objectification*

Objectification refers to degrading a human being to a mere entity or object and evaluating an individual based on her/his physical appearance without giving any consideration to the talents, qualities, or values they possess. In the process of objectification, there are two people involved- one who objectifies, i.e., the *objectifier*, and the other who is subjected to objectification, i.e., the *objectified*. When the same person becomes the 'objectifier' as well as the 'objectified', it is referred to as 'Self-Objectification'. In such a scenario, the person considers one's own self as an object of gratification and treats his/herself as a commodity. American Philosopher Martha Craven Nussbaum (1995), defines objectification as "...treating one thing as another... as an object, what is really not an object, what is, in fact, a human being". Explaining further, she describes seven notions that are central to the idea of treating as an object.

- *Instrumentality*: The objectifier considers the objectified as a tool to serve her/his purpose.
- *Denial of Autonomy*: The objectified is treated as something that lacks self-determination and autonomy.
- *Inertness*: The objectified is considered as inactive and deprived of agency.
- *Fungibility*: The objectified is treated by the objectifier as being interchangeable with things of the same or different types.
- *Violability*: The objectifier regards the objectified as not possessing any boundaries, and as something that can be violated.
- *Ownership*: No self-ownership of the objectified, owned by others, and can be s/he can be bought or sold by others.
- *Denial of Subjectivity*: Not taking into consideration the feeling and experiences of the objectified.

Past research has highlighted that self-objectification is more common in women as compared to men (Oehlhof et al., 2009; Moradi and Huang, 2008; Weltzin et al., 2005), but in recent times, men too are becoming increasingly prone to it, whereby they indulge in constant body monitoring.

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A study by Dwivedi et al. (2021) reported that 77% scored moderately high on objectification. Along similar lines, it has been observed that there has been an increase in body image concerns in men (Johnson et al., 2007) and an increase in steroid intake, excessively high exercise and desire for muscularity (Parent and Moradi, 2011; Daniel and Bridges, 2010), all of which can be related to self-objectifying behaviour. Reasons for self-objectification in women could be attributed to the prejudiced behaviour against them that puts them in a position where they are expected to always look and behave in a certain way and fulfil the criteria of feminine standards set by society. The results of a project by Dove point out that only 4% of women worldwide consider themselves beautiful, and 72% of girls experience immense pressure to look beautiful. In yet other surveys, it was found that 20-40% of men were not happy about the way they look, about their physical appearance, their weight and muscle tone, etc. For instance, in a study by Frederick et al. (2007), it was observed that around 45%-90% of men desired for increased body muscularity. Hence, it can be said that the huge gender differences that prevailed earlier regarding objectification and self-objectification in men and women have started to shrink with time.

1.2 Well-Being

Well-being is “a state of happiness and contentment, with low levels of distress, overall good physical and mental health and outlook, or good quality of life” as defined by the American Psychological Association (APA). It can be categorised into subjective well-being, psychological well-being and social well-being.

- Subjective well-being includes “having high positive emotions, high life satisfaction, and low negative emotions”.
- Psychological well-being (Ryff, 1989; Ryff and Keyes, 1995) focuses on positive functioning and can be understood through its six components:
 - i. *Autonomy*: It caters to the level of independence and self-regulation a person exhibits in terms of behaviour, and whether one performs as per social pressures or by the set personal standards.
 - ii. *Environmental Mastery*: It is the ability to manage situations and choose opportunities that enhance the efficiency of the individual. It also encompasses the competency of a person to create or choose environments that fit her/his needs and principles.
 - iii. *Personal Growth*: Openness to growth and new experiences and working towards expanding horizons comes under personal growth.

Acknowledging the changes and improvement in the self are also a part of this domain.

iv. *Positive Relations*: This aspect revolves around having relationships with others that are warm and affectionate, and understanding how an interpersonal relationship works.

v. *Purpose in Life*: It refers to having a direction and meaning in life, certain goals and objectives that give purpose to one's life.

vi. *Self-Acceptance*: This facet of well-being talks about recognising and accepting all the factors, whether good or bad, that make up a person's self. Self-acceptance also means having a positive outlook towards one's past.

- Social well-being as explained by Keyes (1998) is well-being from the perspective of public and social criteria. It has five dimensions: *social acceptance, social actualisation, social contribution, social coherence, and social integration*.

Yet another categorisation of well-being divides it into 'eudaimonic' and 'hedonic' well-being, which include happiness, life satisfaction, meaning and accomplishment. It has been observed that these two aspects experience a decrease when people are involved in self-objectification (Breines et al., 2008). Koval et al. (2019) also reported heightened negative emotions as a result of self-objectification. Past literature has established links between self-objectification and various aspects of a person's life that are direct or indirect indicators of well-being. For example, self-esteem and positive affect are negatively affected by self-objectification (Adams et al., 2017; Breines et al., 2008), whereas it marks an increase in body shame, appearance anxiety, body surveillance, disgust, guilt, depression, eating disorders, meaningful interpersonal relationships, etc. (Roberts and Gettman, 2004; Sinclair and Myers, 2004; Fredrickson and Roberts, 1997).

India is a country with a stronghold of patriarchal culture. Patriarchy emphasises the behaviour and appearance of men and women, whereby they are expected to maintain a masculine/muscular and feminine/graceful appearance respectively. It then follows that women and men in Indian society are more identified and associated with their bodies. For example, the very image of an ideal man is that of a warrior. Instances from Indian mythology as well informed about the propagated male body image. Lord Ram, the epitome of an ideal man, is usually portrayed in images and movies as having a well-groomed muscular body. This might send out a message to the masses about how a man should look.

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1.3 *The Present Study*

So far, objectification was mostly understood with regard to women, but recently it has been observed that images of men objectification are also gaining prevalence. Men too are exposed to unrealistic standards of body and beauty. Therefore, it becomes imperative to study whether men are influenced by these traps of physical perfection in the present times. In addition to these, objectification has been known to have detrimental psychological outcomes.

Objectives

Following were the objectives of the present study: To study the gender differences in self-objectification among Indian adults. To study the gender differences in psychological well-being among Indian adults. To understand the relationship between self-objectification and psychological well-being among Indian adults. To explore self-objectification among Indian adults.

Hypotheses

Based on these objectives, the following hypotheses were developed for the present study: H1 There will be a significant gender difference in Self-Objectification among Indian adults. H2. There will be a significant gender difference in Psychological Well-Being among Indian adults. H3. There will be a significant relationship between sub-dimensions of self-objectification and psychological well-being among Indian adults.

Keeping these thoughts in mind, the current research study was carried out to understand self-objectification in both men and women and to evaluate its impact on their psychological well-being.

2. Method

2.1 *Research Design*

The current study is an ex-post-facto research as the variables under study, i.e., Self-objectification, and Psychological Well-Being, are already established in the sample and there was no manipulation of variables at the researchers' end. This study attempts to explore the current trends in the said variables among the participants and establish a relationship between them if it exists. Thus, it is exploratory and correlational in nature. Furthermore, a mixed-methods approach was adopted for the collection and analysis of data.

2.2 *Tools*

To tap into the construct of self-objectification, the Self-Objectification Beliefs and Behaviours Scale (SOBBS) developed by Lindner and Tantleff-Dunn (2017) was used. It is a 5-point Likert scale and has a total of 14 statements. It taps two aspects of self-objectification - 'Observer's Perspective' and 'Body as Self' - having seven statements each. The scale has good test-retest reliability, as well as good convergent and discriminant validity.

The Ryff's Psychological Well-Being (PWB) Scale, 42 items version by Carol D. Ryff was used to study the psychological well-being of the participants. The scale is multi-faceted and comprises of six sub-scales: Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance.

2.3 *Sample*

The sample for the current study consisted of 150 adults (75 females, 75 males). The inclusion criteria for the study were 18-30 years of age, general English proficiency, and a stable internet connection. Purposive sampling and Snowball sampling techniques were used for data collection.

2.4 *Procedure*

The participants were approached, and their informed consent was obtained. Those who gave their consent, only their responses were included in the study. The responses were then scored, and data were analysed using SPSS. Statistical measures like the independent t-test and Pearson's correlation were applied. Based on the obtained results, inferences were drawn.

To explore the contributing agents and manifestation/expression of self-objectification, a few participants who scored high on self-objectification were selected randomly and were requested to be part of an interview later. Their answers were examined and further analysed to develop a deeper understanding of the issue of self-objectification and the context in which they occur.

3. **Results**

The obtained data were subjected to appropriate statistical analysis and the results were interpreted in the light of the hypotheses. The results are as follows:

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Table 1.1
t-test Results Comparing Females and Males on Self- Objectification.

Dimensions of Self-Objectification	Gender				t ratio	p-value
	Females		Males			
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Observer's Perspective	19.585	5.969	18.685	8.663	0.716	0.475
Body as Self	14.100	5.313	14.714	8.106	-0.530	0.597
Total Self-Objectification	33.685	9.544	33.400	15.696	0.130	0.897

Note: *- p<0.05, **- p<0.01

(Source: The authors)

Table 1.1 shows that there exists no significant difference (*observer's perspective* $p=0.475$, *body as self* $p=0.597$, *total self-objectification* $p=0.897$) between females and males in the dimensions of self-objectification. Therefore, hypothesis H1 "There will be a significant gender difference in Self-Objectification among Indian adults" was rejected in the current study.

Table 1.2
t-test results comparing females and males on Psychological Well-Being

Dimensions of Psychological Well-Being	Gender				t ratio	p-value
	Females		Males			
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		
Autonomy	27.057	5.288	29.714	5.127	-3.018**	0.003
Environmental Mastery	26.728	4.471	27.000	3.737	-0.390	0.697
Personal Growth	30.157	4.512	30.400	4.281	-0.327	0.744
Positive Relations	30.828	6.580	30.171	5.659	0.633	0.527
Purpose in Life	30.971	5.735	29.685	6.477	1.243	0.216
Self-Acceptance	28.785	6.419	28.857	6.176	-0.067	0.947

Note: *- p<0.05, **- p<0.01

(Source: The authors)

Table 1.2 shows that out of the six dimensions of Psychological Well-Being studied here, one dimension, i.e., Autonomy, showed significant gender differences ($t= 3.018$, $p= 0.003$). Male participants were found to have a higher mean than the female participants in the dimension of Autonomy (Males $M= 29.714$, $SD= 5.127$; Females $M= 27.057$, $SD= 5.288$) as can be seen in Table 1.2. Therefore, hypothesis H2 "There will be a significant gender difference in Psychological Well-Being among young adults" was partially accepted in the present study.

Table 2
Inter-correlation matrix between dimensions of
Psychological Well-Being and Self-Objectification.

Psychological Well-Being	Self-Objectification		
	Observer's Perspective	Body as Self	Total Self-Objectification
Autonomy	-0.335**	-0.311**	-0.356**
Environmental Mastery	-0.005	0.003	0.000
Personal Growth	-0.143	-0.346**	-0.265**
Positive Relations	-0.121	-0.209*	-0.180*
Purpose in Life	-0.342**	-0.378**	-0.396**
Self-Acceptance	-0.210*	-0.132	-0.190*

Note: *- p<0.05, **- p<0.01
 (Source: The authors)

Table 2 shows that various sub-dimensions of Psychological Well-Being significantly correlate with the total as well as the two dimensions of Self-Objectification.

Observer's Perspective dimension relates negatively and significantly with Autonomy $r_{(150)} = (-0.335, p < 0.01)$, Purpose In Life $r_{(150)} = (-0.342, p < 0.01)$, and Self-Acceptance $r_{(150)} = (-0.210, p < 0.05)$.

Body As Self dimension relates negatively and significantly with Autonomy $r_{(150)} = (-0.311, p < 0.01)$, Personal Growth $r_{(150)} = (-0.346, p < 0.01)$, Positive Relations $r_{(150)} = (-0.209, p < 0.05)$, and Purpose In Life $r_{(150)} = (-0.378, p < 0.05)$.

Total Self-Objectification relates negatively and significantly with Autonomy $r_{(150)} = (-0.356, p < 0.01)$, Personal Growth $r_{(150)} = (-0.265, p < 0.01)$, Positive Relations $r_{(150)} = (-0.180, p < 0.05)$, Purpose In Life $r_{(150)} = (-0.396, p < 0.01)$, and Self-Acceptance $r_{(150)} = (-0.190, p < 0.05)$.

Therefore, hypothesis H3 "There will be a significant relationship between sub-dimensions of self-objectification and psychological well-being among Indian adults" was accepted in the present study.

4. Discussion

The present study was conducted with the aim to understand psychological well-being and self-objectification among adults in the Northern part of India. The results are discussed in the following section.

4.1 Gender Difference in Self-Objectification

The results revealed that females and males do not differ significantly in the sub-dimensions of self-objectification, as well as in total self-objectification. Though the previous studies conclude that women go through self-objectification more as compared to men (Oehlhof et al., 2009), it

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has also been observed that in recent times men, especially young adults, are becoming more and more aware of their bodies and are increasingly concerned about their physical appearance (Moradi and Huang, 2008; Weltzin et al., 2005). This could be further backed up by the recent observations in cosmetic surgery which are done with the sole purpose of enhancing one's beauty and looks. Earlier it was mostly women who underwent cosmetic surgery, but lately, there has been a surge in men's aesthetic surgery too. A global report by the American Society of Aesthetic Plastic Surgery (ASAPS) stated that, in the time period between 1997 and 2013, there has been an increase of about 273% in the number of males opting for cosmetic procedures (Sachdev and Britto, 2014). In India too, there has been a relative increase of about 14.6 times in males seeking this surgery in the last decade (Rajan et al., 2021).

In today's world, the media has set unreasonable standards for both males and females which has resulted in the development of an objectified concept of one's self and of body consciousness (Vandenbosch and Eggermont, 2015; Manago et al., 2015). Previous studies have observed that the use of Facebook and magazines correlates positively with self-objectification among women and men (Fardouly et al., 2015; Hanna et al., 2017). Similar results concerning men were observed in the study by Fox and Rooney (2015) who found that men who objectify themselves spend more time on social networking sites. Hence, it could be said that both men and women are subjected to objectification and commodification indiscriminately and the media plays a major role in it. This stands true in the present research as well, as men and women showed on significant differences in self-objectification.

4.2 Gender Difference in Psychological Well-Being

Statistical analysis of data revealed that only the dimension of autonomy in psychological well-being showed a significant difference between males and females, with men having a higher mean value than women. Similar results have been reported in previous studies where men scored higher on the autonomy dimension of psychological well-being (Matud et al., 2019; Maroof and Khan, 2016; Perez, 2012). This could be attributed to the process of socialisation, wherein men enjoy higher levels of independence and control over their lives as compared to women. The roles defined for women are more rigid in nature and women are expected to act in accordance with them. On the other hand, though there are societal roles set for males too, men often have the liberty to behave as they prefer. They

can make choices as per their wishes, while women face the restrictions imposed upon them directly or indirectly by social norms when it comes to making decisions for themselves. This discrimination is shaped not only by socio-cultural forces but is also rooted in the typical setting of the Indian family. One of the prominent ways in which these gender-specific expectations are introduced at the family level is through the allotment of work to girls and boys based on sexual division (Gore, 1977). Women are barred into invisibility and have insufficient decision-making power, all of which makes them behave in ways that are self-limiting (Sivakumar and Manimekalai, 2021).

4.3 *Relationship between Psychological Well-Being and Self-Objectification*

The results of the present study show a significant negative relationship between almost all the dimensions of Self-Objectification and Psychological Well-Being. When individuals involve in self-objectifying behaviour, it tends to hamper their affective states, by increasing their negative emotions and decreasing the positive effects (Koval et al., 2019; Breines et al., 2008). It also aids in the development of anxiety, shame, and guilt, and hinders interpersonal relationships (Roberts and Gettman, 2004; Sinclair and Myers, 2004; Fredrickson and Roberts, 1997). Treating one's self as an object could also diminish the experiences of happiness, life satisfaction, and accomplishments, which are all predictors of well-being. Existing literature also points in this direction where objectification has been found to have negative effects on the well-being of individuals (Mishra, 2020; Winn and Cornelius, 2020; Cheng et al., 2021). In the present study, autonomy and purpose in life were negatively correlated with observer's perspective, body as self, as well as the total self-objectification. Personal growth and positive relations were found to be negatively correlated with body as self and total self-objectification. Self-acceptance showed a negative correlation with observer's perspective and total self-objectification. environmental mastery did not show any relationship with self-objectification. Therefore, it could be said that self-objectification decreases the overall well-being of an individual.

4.4 *Qualitative Analysis*

To develop a deeper understanding of self-objectification, its expression and contributing factors in Indian adults, randomly selected participants (N=50; those who scored high on self-objectification) were interviewed and it was found that irrespective of gender, participants

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diminished their 'self' to just their bodies and were highly concerned about how they looked to others.

Certain themes were identified from the participants' responses. One theme that emerged was '*Body Focused Perceptions*'. When asked to tell about themselves, almost all the participants majorly focused on their physical features, like - "*I am tall, a little too much for girls*", "*I love my hair and feel happy when people appreciate them*", "*I have a perfect body, something that I really admire*", "*I liked dressing up earlier, but now I do not dress up much as I have put on weight and do not look beautiful like I used to*", etc. They also expressed that they prefer being appreciated for how they look than how they perform, and constantly try to achieve the standards that are portrayed in society. This emphasis on physical appearance could be attributed to high exposure to shows that are objectifying in nature. Similar results were reported in a study conducted by Aubrey (2006), where both men and women who watched television shows that were sexually objectified, exhibited an increase in their body appearance-focused self-descriptions; whereas in the context of body surveillance, a strong effect of media was observed only in male participants. At times, women even endure pain in their daily lives to enhance their appearance (Wolf, 2002). They often tend to compare themselves to celebrities. As per The National Eating Disorders Association, this unhealthy comparison gives way to an unhealthy mindset which in turn leads to harmful eating patterns (Coyle, 2020).

Another theme that was identified was '*Preoccupation with Appearance Ideals*'. For instance, when asked about their views on a perfect man/woman, their descriptions mainly referred to a fair complexion, no body hair, being well-groomed; having curves (neither too thin nor fat), beautiful hair, toned body for women; and tall stature, muscular chiselled body, having a beard for men. In continuation to these responses, they were enquired about the basis on which they formed these opinions. '*Social Media*' and '*Entertainment Media*' were the two agents that surfaced from the responses of the participants. Responses pertaining to these themes are - "*The photos of influencers on Instagram are so perfect, they look so perfect, unlike me...(laughs)*", "*I know that in real life these actors and actresses are not how they look in movies, but still I feel a little jealous of them. And I feel angry also because then we too are expected to meet those standards*".

These responses reveal that media is one of the primary contributing factors in promoting objectification. Be it on social media or in the entertainment industry (movies, songs, advertisements), the prevalence of objectification in various forms can be witnessed (Gor, 2018; Davis, 2018;

Sen, 2019). A direct connection between time spent on social networking sites and self-objectification, dissatisfaction with body weight and the desire to be thin (Fardouly et al., 2015; Slater and Tiggerman, 2015; Tiggerman and Miller 2010) has been established in past studies. It was also observed that female Facebook users were more concerned about their body image as compared to female non-users (Tiggerman and Slater, 2013). The same could be said about Instagram: there exists a direct relationship between Instagram use and body surveillance and self-objectification among women (Feltman and Szymanski 2018; Fardouly et al., 2018). A study done by the Dove Self-Esteem project reports that 65-69% of females think that advertisements and media set beauty standards that are unrealistic and cannot be achieved. Therefore, based on the past literature and the results of the present study, media can be considered as a major contributor to objectification.

These results could be attributed to the objectifying environment that both women and men are part of which makes them prone to internalising appearance ideals set by society. Both genders feel the pressure to adhere to unrealistic social standards of physical beauty. Over time, this pressure has grown stronger because of commercial influences through mass media. This pressure leads to unhealthy behaviours and preoccupation with appearance, which compromises their ability to be efficient and accept themselves just the way they are.

Conclusion

The current study was undertaken to understand self-objectification and psychological well-being across Indian males and females. It was observed that women and men do not differ in self-objectification. In psychological well-being, the gender difference was only present in the dimension of autonomy. It could be said that in the present times, males and females, both are subjected to objectifying environments via the media, which in turn hampers their psychological well-being. On one hand, where women are stuck with shaping their bodies perfectly, men too are getting messages of physical perfection. It was also observed that there is a negative correlation between all the dimensions of self-objectification and psychological well-being, except environmental mastery. When the data was studied qualitatively, it was observed that self-objectification expresses itself through body monitoring, descriptions of self, and behaviour that are preoccupied with appearance ideals. Media emerged as a major contributing factor in self-objectification.

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Future studies can consider participants from different age groups, regions as well as cultures which will make the findings more efficient and generalised. They can also explore additional factors (other than media) that contribute to self-objectification and could also tap into shared and unique experiences of different genders in the context of self-objectification.

Funding

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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